

Latent Heat of Evaporation, Density, Temperature, and Composition of Organic Liquids

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The correlation of the structure of organic molecules with their physical properties has been a coveted aim of chemists for a long time. Molecular volume, being one of such physical properties, was seriously studied from an early time. Molecular volumes based on density, measured near the boiling point, were extensively investigated by Koppt, Traube², and Le Bas³. Definite quantitative relationships were observed and atomic values were derived to be used in an additive manner. These values have been useful in spite of certain obstacles, the greatest of which has been the difficulty, if not the impossibility, of comparing molecules in the same or corresponding states. One effort to overcome this difficulty led to the determination of the so-called "Nullpunkt's Volume", which was obtained by the extrapolation of temperature-density curves to absolute zero, by Biltz, Fischer, and Wunneberg⁴. Another promising approach was based upon Guldberg's⁵ rule. Since the boiling point of a substance is approximately two-thirds of its critical pressure, molecular volumes have been compared at temperatures which are some constant fraction of the boiling point. These theoretical modifications of the simple molecular volume concept have been somewhat disappointing in the final analysis.

The most successful attempt in this direction has been the concept of *parachor* by Sugden⁶ based upon the empirical relationship discovered by Macleod⁷ between surface tension and density, and theoretically deduced by Fowler⁸. The parachor gives us a method to compare the molecular volumes of different compounds at the temperature of unit surface tension. This parachor has been found to possess primarily an additive property, the parachor of a compound being the sum of the atomic parachors, with some additional terms where certain structures, such as double and triple bonds and cyclic structures, are present. The chief significance to be attached to a comparison of molecular volumes at constant surface tension instead of at constant temperature, or at a reduced temperature, e.g., the boiling point, is that this method does make some allowance for the effect on molecular volumes of the forces due to molecular attraction. The comparison of parachor with critical volume and mean collision area supplies further evidence for the view that parachor is a true measure of the molecular volume. Mumford and Philips⁹, Vogel¹⁰, Quayle *et al.*¹¹, and Gibling¹² have detected certain shortcomings in Sugden's attractively simple treatment of the parachor as an additive function and modified the values of atomic parachors.

Because of the relationship observed between the parachor and several other properties, other derived properties related to the parachor have been suggested. Bogdan¹³ has suggested the *neoparachor*, which is a function of the molecular volume and the absolute boiling point. Friend and Hargreaves¹⁴ have suggested *rheochor* which is a function of vis-

cosity and molecular volume. Bowden and Jones¹⁵ suggested the *lyoparachor*, which is a function of the internal latent heat of vaporisation and density of a liquid. This was based on the empirical relation found by them among internal latent heat of vaporisation (λ_i), the density of the liquid (D), and the orthobaric density of the vapour (d) at a particular temperature:

$$(\lambda_i = K(D-d)^{4/3})$$

where K is independent of temperature over a wide range,

$$\therefore \frac{\lambda_i^{3/4}}{D-d} = K$$

Multiplying each side by the molecular weight of the liquid (M)

$$\frac{M \cdot \lambda_i^{3/4}}{D-d} = MK = \text{lyoparachor } (\lambda).$$

It is not the purpose of the present paper to criticise the work of Bowden and Jones¹⁵ but the same relationship was found by the author¹⁶ in 1926.

These relationships are as:

$$\lambda_i = K (D-d)^{3/2} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

$$\lambda = K_1 (T_c - T)^{0.45} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

$$D-d = K_2 (T_c - T)^{0.3} \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

where λ_i =internal latent heat of vaporisation, T_c =absolute critical temperature, T =the absolute temperature, D and d are the densities of the liquid and its orthobaric vapour at the corresponding temperature T . Tables I, II, and III show the application of these empirical equations (i), (ii), and (iii) over a wide range of temperature, showing the constancy of K , K_1 , and K_2 .

TABLE I

Values of K at different temperatures for various liquids.

Compounds.	0°.	20°.	40°.	60°.	80°.	100°.	120°.	140°.	160°.	200°.
Benzene	23.80			24.00	24.0	23.90				
Carbon tetrachloride	8.13			8.14	8.14	8.12				8.10
Diethyl ether	26.3	26.2	25.9	25.7		25.7	25.9			
Isopentane	29.2	29.1	28.8	28.7						
Pentane ⁿ	29.6	29.6	29.6	29.7						
Hexane ⁿ	28.1		28.1	28.1	28.2					
Ethyl formate	22.7	22.7	22.7	22.6	22.7					
Ethyl acetate	22.4			22.2	22.2	22.2				
Tin tetrachloride						4.7	4.7	4.7	4.6	4.6
Methanol	51.9			52.4	52.3	51.8				
Ethanol	43.7		45.1	45.2	45.6	45.0	44.8	45.3		

TABLE II

Values of K_1 at different temperatures for various liquids.

Compound.	0°	20°	30°	40°	60°	80°	100°	110°	120°	200°	280°
Ethyl acetate	7.84	7.67			7.67	7.69	7.71				
Diethyl ether	7.94	7.88	7.73	7.68			7.66		7.56		
Benzene	7.74				7.79	7.81	7.74				
CCl ₄	3.79					3.78	3.79		3.79	3.71	
Tin tetra- chloride							2.56	2.55	2.49	2.45	2.52

TABLE III

Values of K_2 at different temperatures for various liquids.

Compound.	0°	20°	80°	120°	140°	150°	160°	200°	250°	280°	300°
Ethyl acetate		5.69	5.70	5.70			5.71	5.78			
Chlorobenzene						5.21	5.20	5.20	5.22		5.30
Benzene	6.08		6.12	6.11		6.13		6.14			
Diethyl ether	6.61	6.60	6.62	6.60	6.59	6.71					
CCl ₄	3.32	3.34	3.35	3.35		3.36		3.37			
Methyl formate	4.99	4.99	5.00			5.05					
Tin tetra-chloride			2.50	2.50		2.50		2.51		2.61	

If equation (i) is multiplied by the molecular weight (M) of the substance,

$$\frac{M}{D-d} \times \lambda_i^{2/3} = M \times K$$

At low temperature, d is very small and can be neglected.

$$\therefore \frac{M}{D} \times \lambda_i^{2/3} = M \times K$$

$$\therefore \text{Molecular volume } (V_m) \times \lambda_i^{2/3} = M \times K$$

If we choose an arbitrary condition such as $\lambda_i^{2/3}=1$, molecular volume (V_m)= $M \times K = p\lambda_i$ (lambdachor). *Lambdachor* ($p\lambda_i$) is thus a nice method of comparing molecular volumes of liquid substances when their internal latent heats of vaporisation are equal. The *lambdachsors* ($p\lambda_i$) were obtained for different types of organic compounds—aliphatic, aromatic, and hydroaromatic hydrocarbons, esters, ketones, aldehydes, nitriles, and amines. From the molecular lambdachsors, atomic lambdachsors for atoms like carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, and nitrogen were calculated. It is generally additive in character, but constitutive effects are also obtained. The values for oxygen are different according as it is in the form of an ether, a ketone, or a carboxylate ester. Double and triple bonds also raise the values. Exaltation is also observed for six-membered rings like benzene, pyridine, naphthalene, or cyclohexane. The values for atomic lambdachsors and other constitutive effects are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Values of atomic lambdachsors.

Carbon	22.0	Oxygen (ester)	578.0
Hydrogen	162.0	Double bond	231.0
Nitrogen	110.0	Triple bond	461.0
Oxygen (ether)	203.0	Six-membered	74.0
Oxygen (ketonic)	410.0	ring	

The experimental and calculated values of $\rho\lambda_i$ agree within experimental error and are shown in Table V for nearly 62 organic compounds of various types. A typical calculation is given for three liquids.

Benzene: $K=24.02$. $M=78$. $\rho\lambda_i$ (obs.)=1873.

$\rho\lambda_i$ (calc.)= $6C+6H$ +values of double bonds + value of six-membered ring.
 $=6+22+6\times 162+3\times 231+74=1871$.

Ethyl butyrate ($C_6H_{12}O_2$): $\rho\lambda_i$ (obs.)=2645.

$\rho\lambda_i$ (calc.)= $6\times 22+12\times 162+578=2654$.

Benzonitrile (C_7H_5N): $\rho\lambda_i$ (obs.)=2304.

$\rho\lambda_i$ (calc.)= $7\times 22+5\times 162+110+3\times 231+461+74$, i.e.

$7C+5H+N+3$ double bonds + triple bond + six-membered ring= 2302 .

TABLE V

No.	Substance.	Formula.	$\rho\lambda_i$		% Diff.	Reference.
			Obs.	Calc.		
A. Hydrocarbons						
1	Isopentane	C_5H_{12}	2083	2054	1.4	Young ²⁵
2	Pentane ^a	C_5H_{12}	2132	2054	3.8	"
3	Hexane ^a	C_6H_{14}	2421	2400	0.9	"
4	Heptane ^a	C_7H_{16}	2753	2746	0.3	"
5	Octane ^a	C_8H_{18}	3095	3092	0.1	"
6	Decane ^a	$C_{10}H_{22}$	3805	3784	0.6	Luginin ²⁰
7	Dipropyl ⁱ	C_6H_{14}	2401	2400	0.1	Young ²⁵
8	Dibutyl ⁱ	C_8H_{18}	3106	3092	0.5	"
9	Amylene	C_5H_{10}	1963	1961	0.1	Berthelot ¹⁷ Schiff ²⁴
10	Hexylene	C_6H_{12}	2311	2307	0.2	Young ²⁵
11	Cyclohexane	C_6H_{12}	2150	2150	0.0	"
12	Methyl cyclohexane	C_7H_{14}	2496	2496	0.0	Kahlenburg ¹⁹ , Luginin ²⁰
13	Benzene	C_6H_6	1873	1871	0.1	Young ²⁵
14	Ethyl benzene	C_8H_{10}	2578	2563	0.6	Schiff ²⁴
15	Propyl ^a benzene	C_9H_{12}	2896	2909	0.5	"
16	Toluene	C_7H_8	2224	2217	0.3	Kahlenburg ¹⁹
17	Mesitylene	C_9H_{12}	2902	2909	0.3	Schiff Brown?
18	<i>o</i> -Xylene	C_8H_{10}	2558	2563	0.2	Brown ¹⁸
19	<i>m</i> -Xylene	C_8H_{10}	2552	2563	0.4	"
20	<i>p</i> -Xylene	C_8H_{10}	2564	2563	0.0	"
21	Naphthalene	$C_{10}H_8$	2802	2819	0.6	Luginin ²⁰ .

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TABLE V (contd.)

No.	Substance.	Formula.	$\rho\lambda_i$		%Diff.	Reference.
			Obs.	Calc.		
22	Ethyl formate	$C_3H_6O_2$	1678	1651	1.5	Young
23	Ethyl acetate	$C_4H_8O_2$	1989	1962	1.4	Young
24	Propyl acetate	$C_5H_{10}O_2$	2314	2308	0.3	Brown
25	Butyl acetate	$C_6H_{12}O_2$	2690	2654	1.4	"
26	Isobutyl acetate	$C_6H_{12}O_2$	2682	2654	1.0	"
27	Isoamyl acetate	$C_7H_{14}O_2$	2987	3000	0.4	"
28	Methyl propionate	$C_4H_8O_2$	1935	1962	1.4	Young
29	Ethyl propionate	$C_5H_{10}O_2$	2295	2308	0.6	"
30	Isoamyl propionate	$C_8H_{16}O_2$	3335	3346	0.3	Brown
31	Isoamyl formate	$C_6H_{12}O_2$	2635	2654	0.7	"
32	Ethyl butyrate	$C_6H_{12}O_2$	2645	2654	0.3	"
33	Ethyl isobutyrate	$C_6H_{12}O_2$	2642	2654	0.5	"
34	Isoamyl butyrate	$C_9H_{18}O_2$	3678	3692	0.4	"
35	Ethyl valerate	$C_7H_{14}O_2$	3001	3000	0.0	Schiff
36	Ethyl isoval rate	$C_7H_{14}O_2$	2988	3000	0.4	"
C. Ethers.						
37	Diethyl ether	$C_4H_{10}O$	1922	1921	0.6	Young
38	Diethyl acetal	$C_6H_{14}O_2$	2763	2806	1.5	Luginin
39	Ethyl propyl ether	$C_5H_{12}O$	2259	2257	0.1	Nagornow ²² & Rotinjanz
40	Ethyl isobutyl ether	$C_6H_{14}O$	2610	2603	0.3	"
41	Anisole	C_7H_8O	2385	2420	1.5	Luginin
D. Nitriles.						
42	Acetonitrile	CH_3CN	1089	1101	1.1	Kahlenburg
43	Propionitrile	C_2H_5CN	1442	1447	0.3	Luginin
44	Butyronitrile	C_3H_7CN	1795	1793	0.1	"
45	Capronitrile	$C_5H_{11}CN$	2501	2485	0.6	"
46	Benzonitrile	C_6H_5CN	2304	2302	0.1	"
E. Aldehydes and ketones.						
47	Acetone	C_3H_6O	1449	1448	0.1	Young
48	Diethyl ketone	$C_5H_{10}O$	2133	2140	0.3	Luginin
49	Methylpropyl ketone	$C_5H_{10}O$	2138	2140	0.1	"
50	Methyl isopropyl ketone	$C_5H_{10}O$	2127	2140	0.6	"
51	Methylbutyl ketone	$C_6H_{12}O$	2478	2486	0.3	"
52	Dipropyl ketone	$C_7H_{14}O$	2820	2832	0.4	"
53	Methylhexyl ketone	$C_8H_{16}O$	3186	3178	0.3	"
54	Acetophenone	C_8H_8O	2635	2649	0.5	"
55	Benzaldehyde	C_7H_6O	2307	2303	0.2	"

TABLE V (contd.)

F. Amines.

No.	Substance.	Formula.	Obs.	Calc.	%Diff.	Reference.
56	Diethylamine	C ₄ H ₁₁ N	1978	1980	0.1	Nadejdin ²¹
57	Anylamine	C ₅ H ₁₃ N	2327	2326	0.0	Kahlenburg
58	Aniline	C ₆ H ₇ N	2122	2143	1.0	Luginin
59	Methylaniline	C ₇ H ₉ N	2467	2489	0.9	"
60	Dimethylaniline	C ₈ H ₁₁ N	2816	2835	0.7	"
61	Pyridine	C ₅ H ₅ N	1793	1798	0.3	Kahlenburg
62	Piperidine	C ₅ H ₁₁ N	2085	2076	0.4	Luginin

If λ ($\rho\lambda_i$) is a true measure of the molecular volume, there should be an intimate relationship between this constant and critical volume (V_c). Table VI shows that this ratio is approximately 6.88, though it varies slightly from substance to substance. The last column gives the ratio of Sugden's²⁶ parachor (P) to the critical volume.

TABLE VI

Substance.	$\rho\lambda_i$.	V_c .	$\rho\lambda_i$.	P/V_c .
Benzene	1872.0	256.1	7.31	0.81
Diethyl ether	1922.0	281.9	6.87	0.75
Ethyl acetate	1988.3	286.0	6.95	0.76
Iso pentane	2083.0	307.2	6.78	0.76
Pentane ^a	2132.0	309.8	6.88	0.75
Propyl acetate	2314.0	344.9	6.71	0.75
Ethyl propionate	2295.0	343.9	6.81	0.74
		Mean	6.88	0.77

Thus it is observed that λ ($\rho\lambda_i$) is nearly nine times Sugden's *parachor* ($\rho\lambda_i = 9P$) for non-associated liquids. For associated liquids it is high (16-23). Mean collision areas (a) of molecules of four different substances are compared with those of Sugden's²⁶ parachor and λ in Table VII. The ratio in the last column is found to be roughly constant. Better agreement cannot be expected since many molecules are not symmetrical and $(\rho\lambda_i)^{2/3}$ is only a rough measure of the molecular cross-section.

TABLE VII

Substance.	a .	$(P)^{2/3}/a$	$(\rho\lambda_i)^{2/3}/a$
Benzene	13.83×10^{-16}	2.52×10^{-16}	10.98×10^{-16}
Ethyl acetate	15.01	2.41	10.47
Propyl acetate	15.11	2.30	10.22
Methane	7.72	2.27	9.92

There is an intimate relationship among λ ($\rho\lambda_i$), critical temperature (T_c), critical volume (V_c), and boiling point (T_b). It is given by

$$\rho\lambda_i = \frac{9}{2} \times \frac{V_c T_c}{T_b}$$

The entropy of most of the unassociated liquids is approximately 20.78, though it varies from 20.5 to 21.05. For benzene and other hydrocarbons, this entropy change (ΔS) is related to lambdachor, critical volume, critical temperature, and boiling point. Therefore the above expression can be written as

$$\rho\lambda_i = \frac{\Delta S \times V_c \times T_0}{4.575 \times T_b} = \frac{\Delta S \times V_c \times T_0}{\sqrt{\Delta S \times T_b}} = \frac{\sqrt{\Delta S} \times V_c \times T_0}{T_b}$$

Table VIII shows this relationship for some typical substances.

TABLE VIII

Substance.	V_c .	T_c .	$\rho\lambda_i$ (calc.)	$\rho\lambda_i$ (obs.)
Benzene	256.4	1.59	1838	1873
Pentane ⁿ	310.2	1.52	2173	2132
Ether	282.0	1.52	1929	1922
Ethyl acetate	286.3	1.55	1989	1989
Acetone	216.6	1.54	1501	1449
Cyclohexane	307.5	1.56	2158	2150

Eötvös²⁷ deduced the general equation, $\gamma [(M_v)]^{2/3} = K(t_c - t)^n$, from the assumption that bodies, which are in corresponding states, are also similar in mechanical respects of the forces between their corresponding parts, and their energies. He found that n was equal to one. This was modified by Ramsay and Shields²⁸, but the best modification was by Katayama²⁹ who gave it the form of

$$\gamma \left(\frac{M}{D-d} \right)^{2/3} = K (t_c - t)^n$$

where $K=2.1$ and $n=1$, for normal liquids. This has given us one of the good methods for determining the molecular weights of liquids from the knowledge of surface tension, density of liquid and vapour, and temperature. When we come to internal heat of vaporisation, which is a similar form of energy, a similar form of equation should hold good, or,

$$\lambda_i \left(\frac{M}{D-d} \right)^{2/3} = K(t_c - t)^n \text{ or } \lambda_i \left(\frac{M}{D-d} \right)^{2/3} = K(t_c - t)^{1/4}.$$

We found that when $n=0.25$, the equation holds good for all normal liquids for temperatures ranging from zero to the critical temperature, as recorded in Table IX

TABLE IX

Values of $\log K$ at different temperatures.

Substance.	0°.	20°.	40°.	60°.	70°.	80°.	90°.	100°.	120°.	140°.
Benzene	2.6729	2.6761	2.6743	2.6751	2.6755	2.6777	2.6758	2.6727	2.6751	
CCl ₄	2.3878				2.3869	2.3868		2.3849		2.3795
Pentane	2.7253		2.7172	2.7243		2.7214		2.7192	2.7259	2.7271
	0°.	140°.	160°.	180°.	200°.	220°.	240°.	260°.	270°.	
Chlorobenzene	2.6254	2.6139	2.6169	2.6205	2.6209	2.6241	2.6283	2.6296	2.6298	

In Table IX, the values of $\log K$ for a particular liquid are constant at different temperatures. This equation thus gives us a new method of determining the molecular weight of non-associable liquids. This method has been verified by us for a number of liquids. Just as Ferguson³⁰ deduced Meleod's empirical relationship from Katayama's equation, it is possible to deduce the empirical relationship, $\lambda_i = K(D-d)^{3/2}$, by substituting the equivalent values of $(D-d)$ in place of (t_c-t) in Katayama's equation:

$$\lambda_i \times \left(\frac{M}{D-d} \right)^{2/3} = K (t_c-t)^{0.25}$$

But $(t_c-t) = K(D-d)^{10/3}$

$$\therefore \lambda_i \left(\frac{M}{D-d} \right)^{2/3} = K (D-d)^{10/3 \times \frac{1}{4}} = K (D-d)^{5/6}$$

$$\therefore \lambda_i \times M^{2/3} = K (D-d)^{2/3 + 5/6}$$

$$\therefore \lambda_i \times M^{2/3} = K (D-d)^{3/2}$$

Thus the fundamental empirical relationship, which is the basis of *lambdachor*, can be deduced from the Eötvös equation which has got the theoretical basis in the case of surface tension from the work of Madelung³¹, Born³², and Brillouin³³. Surface tension and latent heat of vaporisation are different kinds of energy and what applies to surface tension can apply *mutatis mutandis* to latent heat of vaporisation.

Finally as *lambdachor* is more susceptible to constitutive influence than *parachor*, and as its value is much bigger than that of *parachor*, it is much easier to detect the constitutive factors in the molecule. Moreover, it gives a new method of comparing molecular volumes and of determining the molecular weight of non-associable liquids as well as the degree of association in the case of associable liquids. The values suggested for atomic *lambdachors* may require modification in the light of better and more accurate values of latent heat of vaporisation, but this does not affect the fundamental nature of the work and the new approach.

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